

Report on focus group discussion and survey results on the role of libraries during crisis: Lithuanian case

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Abstract:	This report presents findings of an online survey and focus group discussions organized by representatives of Kaunas University of Technology library as partners of international ERASMUS+ project CAELUM. WP2A2 report of CAELUM project analyse the role of academic libraries during crisis, expectations and needs of university community in crisis situations, barrier and gaps academic libraries face when responding to crisis and how libraries can contribute to community resilience during and after crisis.
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Table of Contents

Deliverable Factsheets	2
Partnership	3
Revision history	4
Table of contents	5-6
List of figures	7
Executive summary	8
About the project	9
Research questions	9
Participants	9-10
Methodology	10-11
Focus group discussion	10-11
Online survey	11
Ethical considerations	11
Findings	12
Background	12-14
Theme I: Library Roles During Crises	14-17
Theme II: Expectations and Needs	17-19
Theme III: Barrier and Gaps	19-21
Theme IV: Public Engagement and Community	21-23
Theme V: Integration and Employment	23-26
Conclusions and recommendations	26-28

Report on focus group discussion and
survey results on the libraries during crises

Annex 1	29
Annex 2	30-35

List of Figures

Figure 1. Current role of participants in the survey (n = 72).	10
Figure 2. Crises experienced by survey respondents (n = 72).	12
Figure 3. How respondents usually find information during crisis (n = 72).	13
Figure 4. Experience of receiving library support in a crisis (n = 72).	14
Figure 5: Forms of support expected from libraries during crisis (n = 72).	16
Figure 6: Forms of support expected from libraries during crisis ranked as very important (n = 72).	17
Figure 7: Would respondents feel comfortable approaching library for help (n =72)	19
Figure 8: Would respondents feel comfortable approaching library for help (n =72)	21
Figure 9: What might prevent respondents from using library services in a crisis (n =72)	22
Figure 10: How useful if library offered resources or workshops on how to find a job or traineeship (n =72)	24

Executive summary

This report presents the main findings from the Lithuanian case study conducted as part of the Caelum project, which investigates how university libraries provide support to communities during times of crisis. The data was collected by organizing an online survey targeting the students, academic staff, and library professionals along with a focus group discussion involving international students. Combined, these sources offer important perspectives on how libraries have handled previous crises, the expectations various target groups have during periods of crisis, and the challenges that libraries face while trying to fulfil the needs of users.

The report is structured according to the four main research questions. These questions aim to identify the role of library during crisis, expectations and needs of members of university community have regarding library support in crisis situations, barrier and gaps university libraries face when responding to crisis and how libraries can contribute to community resilience during and after crisis. The last chapter of this report recommendations on how academic libraries can support their communities when facing crises are provided.

About the project

CAELUM (Open science supporting vulnerable communities: empowering university libraries in crisis response) is an Erasmus+ project in the Higher Education sector (2025-2027) that places university libraries in the forefront of crisis response through open science, supporting vulnerable communities and bolstering EU-Ukraine cooperation. Through a series of activities, CAELUM aims to upskill university libraries' staff in innovative and interdisciplinary approaches to crisis response and promote and sustain university libraries-driven open knowledge and civic engagement among HE students and staff for crisis response.

Research questions

In collaboration with CAELUM project partners, the main research questions were developed. These questions aim to understand the role libraries have and could have in a crisis.

RQ1: What has been the libraries' role during crises?

RQ2: What are the expectations and perceived needs of students, academic staff, and library professionals regarding library support in crisis situations?

RQ3: What barriers and gaps have university libraries faced in responding to crises?

RQ4: How can university libraries contribute to public engagement and community resilience during and after crises?

On the basis of these research questions, the questions for the focus group discussion and the online survey were developed.

Each project partner additionally developed their specific research question which is related to partner specific case studies that will be developed and implemented in the following project stage Work package 3 (WP3). Kaunas University of Technology Library aims to identify how the library can provide support to international students searching for employment or traineeship.

The partner specific research question as follows:

RQ5: How can the library support international students looking for employment or traineeship?

Participants

According to CAELUM project application in this study were invited to participate members of academic community: students, academic staff, library staff, administrative staff, citizen scientists and others.

All these representatives of the academic community filled in online survey. In total 72 responses were received.

International students currently studying at Kaunas University of Technology were invited to participate in a focus group discussion." In total 6 respondents took part in focus group discussion: five PhD students and one MA student.

Figure 1. Current role of participants in the survey (n = 72).

Based on data depicted in Figure 1, the biggest part of respondents in this online survey were library staff (n = 38), followed by academic staff (n = 21), students (n = 6), administrative staff (n = 5). In addition, respondents represent different age ranges. Major part of respondents was between 46 and 60 years (n = 25), followed by participants in age range between 36 and 45 (n = 16), the third biggest group were individuals over 61 years old (n = 13), the smallest part of respondents indicated they belong to youngest age range between 18 and 25 (n = 10) and between 26 and 35 age range (n = 5). Participants from all target groups and age groups were represented in this online survey it helps to get a broader understanding of what role a library can have when society members are facing crisis.

Methodology

Focus group discussion

A focus group discussion was conducted on 27th of May, 2025. In this discussion participated 6 respondents (5 PhD students and 1 MA student from KTU), discussion was moderated by 2 moderators. A face-to-face focus group discussion in English language was organized in the premises of University Campus Library (KTU) following

a semi-structured interview guide developed collaboratively by CAELUM project partners. The focus group questions were agreed in advance at consortium level, KTU added 2 additional questions related to employability as this theme is of the case study that KTU will implement in WP3. The questions asked during focus group discussion are available in Annex 1.

Online survey

Using Microsoft Forms tool an online survey both in Lithuanian and English language was prepared. Online survey questions were agreed in advance at consortium level, KTU added 1 additional open-ended question related to the topic of their theme - employability. This anonymous online survey was disseminated on a national level among students, researchers, academic librarians, university administration and was publicly accessible from 2nd of June until 15th of June. In total 72 respondents filled in this survey. The questions of the survey in English are available in Annex 2.

Ethical considerations

The researchers contacted the University's Research Ethics Committee about the ongoing survey and focus group discussion. Research ethics approval was obtained for the study to comply with ethical issues while ensuring the protection of personal data. Online survey participants and focus group discussion participants were informed about the CAELUM project, its aims, where and how data will be collected, used and anonymized. Both focus group discussion participants and online survey participants were asked questions that were agreed upon by all CAELUM project partners. Informed consent form for focus group discussion was sent to participants by e-mail in advance. The content of the informed consent form was additionally re-presented to the participants before the start of the focus group discussion and all participants confirmed their understanding by signing the form. The focus group discussion was recorded, recorded audio file was uploaded to Microsoft 365, the transcribe feature was applied it converted speech to a text transcript with each speaker individually separated, finally transcript was reviewed manually, sensitive data was anonymized, and afterwards audio recording was deleted.

Findings

Focus group discussion and online survey aimed to explore experiences, expectations, and reflections on the role of university libraries in crises. The following themes were covered during discussion: experience with crisis contexts, library roles during crisis, expectations and needs, barriers and gaps, public engagement and community resilience, integration and employment. These activities aimed to gather diverse perspectives on the roles of libraries during crises and their role in civic engagement.

Background

Participants of this survey were asked what type of crisis has affected them the most. Majority of participants indicated it was war or armed conflict (n = 27, 37%), the other most popular answer was pandemic or health crisis (n = 21, 29%) while some participants selected the following answers: mental health or well-being challenges (n = 12, 17%), political turbulence (n = 5, 7%), information overload (n=4, 6%), disinformation during emergencies (n = 2, 3%) and climate related crisis (n = 1, 1%). As shown in Figure 2, the responses are distributed accordingly.

Figure 2. Crises experienced by survey respondents (n = 72).

In focus group discussion participants were asked the same question. They indicated that they faced the following crisis: war, political and economic crisis, mental and emotional crisis,

financial crisis, language barrier, unemployment, integration crisis. Participants of our focus group discussion were international students they often talked about political, safety and economic crisis they faced in their home countries before arriving to study at Kaunas University of Technology.

“Political and economic crisis, was very high. Right now it's high, but I left 10 years ago, so I didn't really experienced that. But I do think about it ... And there is also, I would say, national security in a way and safety crisis ... It's not safe to go on the streets. There's racketeering, corruption, people getting killed.”

Students also explained that majority crises they have encountered were caused by war.

“The war had the most negative consequences and it was really bad...Like in terms of mental health, in terms of situation with the visa or residence permit, in terms of housing...”

In addition, survey participants were asked how do they find information during crisis. The most common source was news media (n = 48, 26%), the second most common source social media (n = 40, 22%), the third source friends/family (n=30, 16%) and the following resources government websites (n = 24, 13%), university websites or communication (n =16, 9%), academic journals or research sources (n = 13, 7%), library channels (n = 10, 5%), other (n = 3, 2%). As shown in Figure 3, the responses are distributed accordingly.

Figure 3. How respondents usually find information during crisis (n = 72).

The results of the online survey suggest that during periods of crisis people mostly trust information provided by news media and social media channels as well as information received from relatives and friends. While academic resources are used less frequently, libraries are also mentioned as one of the least popular resources to receive information during crisis. Results show that people do not choose the library as their first source of information provider in a crisis.

Respondents indicated that the most common crises they have experienced are war, pandemic and mental health crisis these themes will be mostly covered in this report and recommendations how library can provide support to people experiencing these crisis will be presented.

Theme I: Library Roles During Crises

In survey and focus group discussion we aimed to explore how people perceive, understand and respond to crisis they experience and what kind of role academic libraries have or could have while providing support to individuals experiencing crisis.

Respondents were asked did they ever received support from library during crisis. More than half of respondents replied that they have never received support from library during crisis (n=40, 56%), whereas other individuals responded that they are not sure if received support (n =19, 26%) and the smallest part of participants claimed that they received support from libraries (n = 13, 18%). The distribution of responses is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Experience of receiving library support in a crisis (n = 72).

Respondents who replied yes, were asked to give an example. One of the students provided the following answer "Emotional conversations/Workshops organized by the staff", whereas

librarians provided these responses: "information", "book chapters were scanned and emailed when the library was closed over the pandemic", "information on how to handle crisis", "emotional support", "emotional support, a chance to feel that you are not alone", responses received from academic staff focused on a more safe place in the library and access to academic resources

"In a broader sense, library spaces provide a slightly more safe place to work (when you need to be away from your usual work environment, for example when experiencing anxiety). I was also able to access the literature I needed at a certain point, as access was bought out (to some medical publications)".

Variety of answers indicated that the library provided a broad range of support for individuals experiencing crisis. It was emotional support, recommendations on how to handle crisis, access to library resources, workshops, secluded library spaces. In addition, after giving examples of support that academic libraries provided respondents were asked what kind of support they would expect from a library during crisis.

To find out in which areas of activity the library could provide support to people in crisis, survey participants were asked which form of support would they expect from library. Majority of participants answered internet or Wi-Fi (n = 51, 17%), the second most popular answer – access to curated information (n = 38, 13%), followed by charging stations (n = 34, 11%), online library services (n = 28, 9%), training sessions and courses (n = 23, 8%), cultural events and social interactions (n = 22, 7%), help with government forms or aids (n = 20, 7%).

Other less often indicated areas how library could support people in crisis were the these: mental health support or safe environment (n = 18, 6%), emergency supplies (n = 17, 6%), support for research or community projects (n = 17, 6%), guidance for using academic databases (n = 12, 4%), help with job seeking and employment (n = 11, 4%), finally, 6 respondents indicated that they would not expect anything from the library. The full distribution of responses is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Forms of support expected from libraries during crisis (n = 72).

International students who participated in focus group discussion indicated that the crisis they experience is closely related to aspects of integration into new country and community and they would need help to overcome challenges like unemployment, language barrier, loneliness, lack of information about Lithuanian culture, feeling of being lost.

"You know, but I think like library can provide a guide for something related to Lithuania, like someone is searching for a job, they can provide some information or guideline like what should you do. This is the steps and this is the place and you can start from".

Several respondents shared their experience that they came from the society where people are more open, extroverted, less reserved and in Lithuanian people are "colder".

"I would say it is also necessary for the international students to know the culture before coming to Lithuania, so maybe there is a course to teach international students to learn about Lithuania that could help avoid cultural shock."

Difficulties to find new friends and lack of communication was also one of the issue international students elaborated on.

"And thinking about those communities, it's really good the community. If we build the community, we can come together, time to time, discuss in Lithuanian language we can share information. This is all good."

While majority of respondents in times of crisis from the libraries would expect to receive services and resources which are traditionally associated with emergency situations like: access to internet and Wi-Fi, access to curated information, charging stations and online library services, the results from focus group discussion depicted that participants expect library to provide support to navigate difficulties such as joblessness, language obstacles, social isolation, unfamiliarity with Lithuanian culture, and a general sense of confusion or disorientation.

Theme II: Expectations and Needs

This section identifies the types of support respondents would need from their library during a crisis situation. It focuses on identifying what kind of assistance individuals would consider most important if a crisis happened tomorrow and what specific services or role they would expect the library to provide during such a time.

In the survey respondents were provided with the list of needs which may rise when facing crisis and asked to rate these needs, using a five-point Likert scale (1 – not important at all, 5 – very important). Some of the needs provided in the list are usual library services for instance access to credible, accurate, and curated information, internet access, online library access whereas other needs are not as often associated with the library services like support for mental health, access to physical space or shelter, emergency information updates etc. According to survey results majority of respondents identified the following need as very important: reliable internet access – 73,6%, emergency information updates – 68,1%, access to credible, accurate and curated information – 66,7 % . Meanwhile, needs that were the least often identified as very important when experiencing crisis were assistance with digital tools – 25%, opportunities for collaboration or problem solving with others 23,4 %, being part of the solution 12,5 %. Distribution of needs in percentages that were ranked as very important is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Forms of support expected from libraries during crisis ranked as very important (n = 72).

The top needs that respondents expect library address in crisis situation were reliable internet, emergency information updates as well access to credible, accurate and curated information. It indicates that in crisis situations, people expect libraries to provide essential digital connectivity and accurate information to help individuals make informed decisions and stay connected.

Participants of focus group discussion were asked if crises occurred tomorrow what kind of support would be most important to you. Some of participants indicated that library could be "the safest place as a shelter", also it was mentioned that library could be a good channel to receive up to date information about current situation and receive instructions what to do in case of emergency. While other respondent explained that it would be very useful if library could provide information for international students how to find a job in Lithuania:

"You know, but I think like library can provide a guide for something related to Lithuania, like someone is searching for a job, they can provide some information or guideline like what should you do. This is the steps and this is the place and you can start from..."

The necessity of getting consultation in the library was also expressed by another participant. One of the participants shared her personal story when being an exchange student in another country she used the service provided by the library:

"I did an exchange I remembered in <...> and one thing that the library had was this like kind of consultation desk. There was helped by volunteer students like locals who basically would help you with any questions you might have as a foreigner, for example. I will get a letter from the government that I don't understand because it's not in my native language and they would help me out. <...> You have to do just not this kind of like having quick consultation about anything and even if they don't know the answer, they would guide you to where you should go and look for the information. So that was very helpful."

The results show that in a crisis, people mainly expect libraries to provide internet access and trustworthy information. These are seen as the most important ways libraries can help. Some participants also mentioned that libraries could be safe places to go, and useful for getting updates, advice, or support. Whereas discussions with international students shows that libraries could play a bigger role in helping the community during difficult times, not just with resources, space and internet

connection, but also with consultations, guidance on how to find a job or deal with daily issues in a foreign country.

Theme III: Barriers and Gaps

This section explores the challenges and barriers that may prevent individuals from seeking or receiving support from libraries during times of crisis. Through examining questions about comfort, trust, accessibility, and awareness, it aims to understand why some people might hesitate to approach libraries for help. By identifying these obstacles — whether practical, social, or emotional — we can begin to consider what changes might make libraries more approachable, supportive, and responsive in times of crisis.

Most of respondents answered positively to a question would they feel comfortable approaching library for help 57 %, whereas 32 % were not sure and 11 % responded that they would not feel comfortable approaching library for help in crisis. The distribution of responses is presented in Figure 7 as percentages.

Figure 7. Would respondents feel comfortable approaching library for help (n =72)

Respondents who answered no or not sure were asked to identify the reason why they would not feel comfortable. Majority of respondents replied that they do not consider library as an organization which would help in times of crisis and lack of information what kind of help could be suggested. Those are the answers they provided:

"I am not sure how library can help in crisis", "There is insufficient sharing of information on what help is available", "For confidence, it is necessary to have knowledge about what the library can offer in a crisis situation, not just hope", "Don't have a habit of asking questions 'live'. All of the important info I can and do find online. If there is no previous advertisement or government recommendations about contacting libraries during crisis, or what libraries can do in a crisis, I'll probably search other official sources, than go and ask if they are open and what can they (or I) do"

The very similar point of view was expressed in focus group discussion participants stated that they do not know what kind of help library could suggest in crisis, still it could be a good niche.

Some respondents in online survey suggested ideas how library can support community in crisis context *"unless you need temporary shelter and internet", "Not sure, if there is a bomb shelter", "Unless the library is converted into a hospital. Otherwise, the role of the library as a crisis aid seems strange, to put it mildly".* Whereas others had doubts if library is the right institution to provide this kind of help *"Because a library must not be the first instance of help, and if it would happen, it would be uncomfortable because of the failure of other institutions", "There are other places where more helpful support can be found", "A library is not associated with an institution that can manage a crisis because it is often the target".* These responses suggest that respondents might have in mind war or armed conflict when thinking about crisis.

To understand better what might prevent respondents from using library services in a crisis respondents were asked to select from the list of reasons provided. The most often indicated reason library is closed (n= 61, 28%), followed by library has no internet access (n = 38, 18%), library location is hard to reach (n=37,17%), didn't know library could help (n = 32, 15%) as well as other reasons indicated in Figure 8.

Figure 8. What might prevent respondents from using library services in a crisis (n =72)

While a majority of respondents (57%) feel comfortable approaching libraries for help during a crisis, a significant portion (43%) either feel uncertain or uncomfortable doing so. This uncertainty stems from a lack of awareness about the types of support libraries can offer during emergencies, as well as practical barriers such as closures, limited internet access, and difficult locations. Additionally, there is a prevalent perception that libraries are not traditionally seen as crisis-response institutions, especially in severe scenarios like armed conflict. This leads to the need of better communication about libraries' potential roles in crises and more proactive integration of crisis-related services to enhance public trust and accessibility.

Theme IV: Public Engagement and Community

This section looks at how people think about the role of libraries in helping communities, especially during hard times. The goal is to understand whether people think libraries can play an important role in supporting their communities, what kind of help they expect, and what services libraries could offer during difficult times. The answers also show how libraries are currently seen and how they could do more to bring people together and provide support when it's needed most.

Respondents were asked if they took part in any community-focused events at their library. The proportion of those who participated 42 % is very similar to the proportion that have not

took part 40%, in addition 18% of respondents are not sure if they took part or not. The distribution of responses is presented in Figure 9 as percentages.

Figure 9. Distribution of have respondents participated in any community-focused events at their library (n =72)

Participants who indicated that they participated in community – focused events were asked what kind of event it was. A diverse variety of responses were received:

“safety training sessions, celebration of anniversaries of academic community members, commemoration events, training sessions organized by the library, cultural and educational events, public lectures, conferences, exhibitions, concerts at the library, freshmen events, book presentations, openings of exhibitions, charity auctions, fundraisers etc”.

Some of the participants informed that they took part in library organized events directly were related to crisis:

“I took part in an event on crises and disinformation and how to deal with them at the University Campus Library”, “Red Cross training, various resilience trainings”, “Various crisis mitigation trainings”, “Safety training sessions”, “events for refugees”.

Whereas participants of focus group discussion emphasized the importance of community building as well as continuation of provided services:

"I think like if library provide any services, it's better from time to time. I mean it should be continuous, <...>So in this case people will be active in the community", "And I think yes, and the community should be built before the crisis. So, in this case, they know this community and they know they can receive the help during or after. But if it's only for the crisis will happen, no one will be aware of this".

These answers show that libraries already organize a wide range of community-focused events. Some events directly addressed crisis-related topics such as disinformation, resilience, and support for refugees, demonstrating the library's active role in responding to contemporary social challenges and serving as a community support hub. Additionally, insights from the focus group discussions emphasized the importance of consistent and ongoing community-building efforts, with participants noting long-term engagement is essential for creating a strong, supportive network that can be relied upon both during and outside of crises.

Theme V: Integration and Employment

This section presents the challenges people face in their academic and personal lives respondents were asked how living in different countries have affected their studies or everyday life. In addition, the questions looked at whether they had any problems joining the local community or finding a job or traineeship. These questions help give a clearer picture of the difficulties some people may face while studying or living in a new place.

Online survey respondents were asked would they find it useful if their library offered resources or workshops on how to find a job or traineeship. Majority of participants – 60% agreed that it would be useful, 23% indicated they are not sure and 17% responded negatively. The distribution of responses is presented in Figure 10 as percentages.

Figure 10. How useful if library offered resources or workshops on how to find a job or traineeship.

Participants of focus group discussion named variety of reasons why they had difficulties integrating into local community and finding a job. The most often mention reason was language barrier, respondents had different opinions on this topic some participants explained that many Lithuanians can speak in English quite fluently and they do not face language barrier while others explained that in order to fully integrate into local community, they have to speak in Lithuanian excellently.

“you literally want to indulge yourself, literally want to live here for a longer period of time, then definitely yeah. You need to get the Max knowledge of Lithuanian, not the A1, A2 and B1. You must be C2 to actually absorb the Lithuanian energy prop”.

Participants shared different experiences related to job search, some participants claimed that they successfully found a job while others faced challenges as they have visa and residence permit issues. In addition, in focus group discussion participants explained that they find it difficult to integrate in local community as they do not socialize with local people.

“we are not exactly moving forward because you know after having came here we not properly integrate with these communities.<...> We actually boxed up ourselves. We actually not getting out of our comfort zone.

Whereas other participant explained that a person should take personal responsibility if he wants to integrate into the local community, he should be more proactive himself.

One of the participants pointed out that he faced challenges to register to Lithuanian language courses via Lithuanian employment website as the website was only in Lithuanian language.

While the other participant shared his personal story and explained that companies face difficult procedures when trying to employ a foreign person.

"I can talk from my experience. So basically, when I first came to Lithuania, I was doing a traineeship at a company. So, I found it while I was abroad. And that was all good. But at the end of the training ship, when I wanted to look for a job, well, first, the company wanted to hire me. They had this intention at the beginning. So, before I ended my internship, we were in talks with that. Once they realised how hard it was to make the documentation to hire me, they suddenly changed their mind and said sorry, we can't help you. So that was rough".

In conclusion, most people in the survey said it would be helpful if libraries offered job-related help like workshops or resources. The focus group discussion showed that many international students face problems finding jobs and joining the local community, mainly because of language barriers, visa issues, and not knowing how to connect with locals. Some believe it's also up to the person to be more active in trying to fit in. Overall, both institutional and personal effort are needed to make it easier for newcomers to find jobs and successfully integrate into local community.

Conclusions and recommendations

The findings of the online survey and focus group discussion organized in Lithuania revealed that in times of crisis, individuals primarily turn to news media, social media, and personal networks such as friends and family for information. Academic resources and libraries, by contrast, are among the least utilized sources during such periods. This suggests that libraries are not currently perceived as primary or immediate providers of crisis-related information.

The survey findings reveal that while a majority of respondents feel comfortable seeking help from libraries during a crisis, a significant part of respondents responded they remain uncertain or uncomfortable doing so. This hesitation is largely attributed to a lack of awareness about the support libraries can provide in emergencies. Furthermore, there is a prevailing perception that libraries are not traditionally viewed as crisis-response institutions, particularly in the context of severe emergencies such as armed conflicts. This perception limits public trust and reduces the likelihood that individuals will turn to libraries in critical situations.

The survey results indicate that during times of crisis, most respondents expect libraries to offer traditional emergency-related services such as access to the internet and Wi-Fi, charging stations, curated information, and online library services. These expectations reflect a practical and immediate need for reliable infrastructure and information.

However, insights from the focus group discussions reveal a broader and more nuanced set of expectations. Participants expressed a desire for libraries to provide support beyond basic services, specifically in helping individuals navigate complex personal and social challenges. These include job loss, language barriers, social isolation, unfamiliarity with Lithuanian culture, and a general sense of disorientation during crises. This contrast highlights the evolving role of libraries as not only information providers but also community support centers.

The findings indicate that libraries are already engaged in a broad range of community-focused activities, some of which directly address crisis-related issues such as disinformation, resilience, and refugee support. These initiatives highlight the library's evolving role as an active responder to contemporary social challenges and a trusted community support hub.

Moreover, insights from focus group discussions reinforce the importance of sustained, long-term community engagement. Participants emphasized that consistent efforts to build and maintain community networks are crucial — not only for strengthening social ties during stable times but also for ensuring reliable support systems are in place when crises occur.

The survey results indicate strong support for libraries to offer job-related assistance, such as workshops, guidance, and access to relevant resources. This reflects a clear public demand for libraries to play a more active role in supporting employment particularly during times of crisis.

Focus group discussions further revealed that many individuals — especially newcomers — face significant challenges in finding employment and integrating into the local community. Key barriers include language difficulties, visa-related limitations, and a lack of knowledge about how to connect with local communities. While some participants acknowledged the importance of personal initiative in overcoming these challenges, the consensus was that institutional support is equally essential. These findings highlight the dual responsibility of individuals and institutions in fostering successful integration.

Based on the results of the focus group discussion and the survey, it is clear that the library already provides a number of services and resources that are needed by communities facing crises. Unfortunately, the public does not know about it and often does not associate the library with an institution that provides crisis support, even though the range of crises faced by individuals can be very broad. Libraries should focus on the following areas in order to strengthen their position in supporting the community in times of crisis:

1. Promote available services during emergencies (e.g., internet access, charging stations, emergency updates, safe spaces).
2. Suggest real-time updated emergency information in multiple languages and formats to serve diverse populations.
3. Provide practical assistance such as job search resources, career workshops, and consultation services, particularly for newcomers and vulnerable groups.
4. Offer volunteer-run help desks to assist with cultural navigation and basic bureaucratic questions.
5. Provide materials, guidance, courses that help newcomers understand local systems and culture.
6. Keep organizing events and programs on topics such as mental health, disinformation, and civic resilience to build trust and strengthen community ties that can be activated in times of crisis.
7. Ensure physical and digital access to library services remains available during crises.
8. Collaborate with institutions that provide social services such as employment agencies, institutions organizing language courses, social and refugees centers.

The findings of this study reveal a complex picture: libraries are valued as stable, trustworthy, and emotionally supportive environments, yet their potential in formal crisis remains underrecognized and underutilized. By following these recommendations, academic libraries

Report on focus group discussion and
survey results on the libraries during crises

can better meet the evolving needs of their communities and reinforce their position as resilient and inclusive spaces in times of uncertainty.

Annex I

Focus group discussion questions

I Experience with Crisis Contexts

- What kinds of crises have you experienced or thought about?
- How have these situations affected your research or personal life?
- Where would you turn first for help in a crisis, and why?

II Library Roles During Crises

- Do you consider libraries as trusted institutions in your community? Why or why not?
- Have you ever received help or support from a library during a crisis?
- How did the library respond (or could have responded) to the crisis during that time?

III Expectations and Needs

- If such a crisis occurred tomorrow, what kind of support would be most important to you?
- What would you expect from your library in this situation?

IV Barriers and Gaps

- What are the main barriers that prevent libraries from supporting people in this specific crisis?
- Are there reasons why you or others might not seek help from a library? If yes, how could we change it?

V Public Engagement & Community Resilience

- Can you imagine a library being a place for community action or support? If yes, then how?
- In your opinion, how can libraries build stronger communities during or after a crisis?

CASE SPECIFIC QUESTIONS

VI Integration and Employment

- Have you had difficulties integrating into the local community? If yes, please specify.
- Have you had difficulties finding a job or traineeship? If yes, please specify

Annex II

Survey questions

I Background information

1. Age *(select one option)*

18-25

26-35

36-45

46-60

61+

Prefer not to say

2. What is your current role within the academic community? *(Select the one you identify with the most)*

Student

Academic staff (e.g. lecturer, researcher)

Library staff

Administrative or support staff

Citizen scientist

I am not a member of the academic community

Other: _____

3. What type of crisis has affected you the most? *(Select one option)*

War or armed conflict

Political turbulence

Pandemic or health crisis

Mental health or well-being challenges in academic life

Information overload and challenges related to open science in research

Climate related crisis (e.g., heatwave, drought, flooding)

Disinformation during emergencies (e.g., war, disasters)

Problems with social integration or job opportunities for international students

Barriers faced by disabled people (e.g., access, inclusion)

Other: _____

4. How do you usually find information during a crisis? *(Select all that apply)*

Social media

News media

Government websites

University websites or communication

Friends/family

Library channels

Academic journals or research sources

Other: _____

II Library Roles During Crises

5. Have you ever received support from a library during a crisis? Support could include practical help, information, or emotional support. *(Select one option)*

Yes

No

Not sure

6. If yes, what kind of support did you receive?

Open question

7. In a crisis situation, which forms of support would you expect or seek from a library? *(Select all that apply)*

Access to curated information

- Internet or Wi-Fi
- Charging stations
- Physical space for study/work
- Mental health support or safe environment
- Cultural events and social interaction
- Help with government forms or aid
- Help with job seeking or employment support
- Emergency supplies (masks, flashlights, etc.)
- Online library services (ebooks, databases, etc.)
- Guidance for using academic databases
- Training sessions and courses
- Support for research or community projects that respond to the crisis
- I wouldn't expect anything from a library
- Other: _____

III Expectations and Needs

8. When facing a crisis, how important would each of the following be for you personally? Some of these needs may be supported by libraries, others may not. Please rate how important each would be to you personally in a crisis. (Rate each from "Not at all important" to "Very important")

	Not at all important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Important	Very important
Access to credible, accurate, and curated information					
Reliable internet access					
Access to physical space or shelter					

Community connection					
Support for mental health					
Online library access					
Emergency information updates					
Assistance with digital tools					
Being part of the solution					
Opportunities for collaboration or problem-solving with others					
Feeling informed and involved					

9. What would make a library feel like a supportive and safe space during a crisis (e.g., space, staff, resources)?

Open question

IV Barriers and Support Gaps

10. What might prevent you from using library services in a crisis? (Select all that apply)

Library is closed

Difficult to find up-to-date information from the library website and social media channels

Library location is hard to reach

Library is not accessible or inclusive for disabled users

Library has no internet access

Didn't know library could help

Negative past experiences at the library

Lack of trust in libraries

Other: _____

11. Would you feel comfortable approaching a library for help in crisis? (select one option)

Yes

No

Not sure

12. If you answered "No" or "Not sure," please explain why:

Open question

V Public Engagement and Community Support

13. Do you agree with the following statement: Libraries can play a meaningful role in supporting communities during crises.

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

14. Have you ever participated in any community-focused events or activities at your university library? (Select one option)

Yes

No

Not sure

15. If yes, what kind of activity or event was it?

Open question

16. What activities or services could a library offer to support your community in difficult times?

Open question

17. Would you find it useful if your library offered resources or workshops on how to find a job or traineeship?

Yes

No

Not sure

18. Do you have anything to add?

Open question